

Deep Learning Application for Monitoring Handwritten Spirals in Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract— Parkinson's disease (PD) is a prevalent neurodegenerative disorder that affects the central nervous system and progressively impairs the control of voluntary movements. The growing body of published research in this field demonstrates the increasing attention that spiral analysis (SA) has attracted in studies focused on the diagnosis and monitoring of PD. SA-based detection methods have shown superior performance compared to traditional approaches involving clinical evaluations, laboratory tests, and neuroimaging, largely due to their practicality and cost-efficiency. This study investigates the potential of spiral drawing tasks as a tool for monitoring Parkinson's disease by applying machine learning (ML) techniques to assess disease status. Specifically, four convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures—VGG16, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, and Xception—were employed to classify individuals into two groups—Parkinson's Disease (PD) and Control—and to detect disease stages within the PD group based on the Hoehn and Yahr scale across multiple data collection sessions. Classification performance was assessed using accuracy and F1-score metrics. The results demonstrate that spiral-based assessments, combined with ML approaches, can effectively support both the diagnosis and longitudinal monitoring of Parkinson's disease progression.

Keywords — *Machine learning, spirals analysis, Parkinson's disease, tremor, convolutional neural network*

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) affects approximately 2–3% of individuals over 65 and is recognised as the second most common neurodegenerative disorder worldwide. Its primary neuropathological hallmarks include intracellular inclusions containing α -synuclein aggregates and the progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurones in the substantia nigra, resulting in dopamine deficiency in the striatum [1]. In addition to motor impairments, PD is associated with a variety of nonmotor symptoms that further contribute to overall disability. Although clinical diagnosis is primarily based on the presence of bradykinesia and key motor symptoms such as tremor, postural instability, and rigidity, it is important to consider the heterogeneity of patient profiles and lifestyles when evaluating functional impairments. [2].

Motor manifestations, including gait disturbances, resting tremor, postural instability, and muscular rigidity,

progressively restrict voluntary motor control, making everyday tasks—such as brushing teeth or stirring with a spoon—increasingly challenging. Commonly observed phenomena include freezing of gait, characterised by brief episodes of motionlessness, and micrographia, a condition in which handwriting becomes progressively smaller and less legible [3].

The diagnostic process for PD is multifaceted, typically involving neurological assessments, neuroimaging techniques, and the observation of a patient's response to dopaminergic treatment. Among these, tremor assessment plays a central role and may be performed by clinical specialists or through computational methods. In this context, spiral analysis (SA) has emerged as a promising non-invasive and accessible technique for quantifying motor function in PD. By evaluating hand-drawn spirals, SA extracts clinically relevant features such as tightness, uniformity, drawing velocity, applied pressure, and task duration—providing objective metrics for assessing motor deficits and disease severity [4].

The Archimedean spiral remains the most widely adopted graphical task in tremor-related studies. It enables the quantification of motor abnormalities—such as tremor, bradykinesia, and micrographia—via kinematic parameters including drawing speed, amplitude, frequency, and temporal features. However, analytical tools developed for the Archimedean spiral may not generalise well to other drawing tasks, and comparative studies across different graphical forms remain limited. While digital platforms such as tablets, smart pens, and inertial measurement units have gained traction in research, traditional pen-and-paper methods continue to offer significant clinical advantages, particularly in terms of simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and widespread applicability. Furthermore, the incorporation of computational analysis ensures greater consistency, objectivity, and reproducibility in symptom evaluation. [citefolador2021opensource](#).

Accurate classification of tremor severity and its progression—whether improving, worsening, or remaining stable—is vital for tailoring treatment strategies to individual patients. In this regard, ensemble methods that combine multiple classifiers can enhance diagnostic accuracy by integrating the complementary strengths of different algorithms [5].

A. Theoretical Framework and Objectives

The central hypothesis of this study is that the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to hand-drawn spiral images enables accurate classification of Parkinson's Disease (PD) across various stages, thereby facilitating more objective and scalable disease monitoring. The primary objective is to develop a CNN-based classification tool for the detection and staging of PD using spiral drawings created with pen and paper. The specific objectives of this research are as follows:

(1) Develop a standardized protocol for spiral data collection using pen-and-paper tests; (2) Acquire samples from two groups: individuals clinically diagnosed with PD and age-matched healthy controls; (3) Digitize all collected drawings at high resolution to preserve data fidelity; (4) Preprocess and resize the images using the R programming language; (5) Train CNN-based models in MATLAB to classify disease stages; (6) Perform statistical analyses to compare the performance of CNN architectures between groups.

Currently, tremor assessment in PD is guided by several components of the Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS), such as postural tremor, kinetic tremor, resting tremor in the upper limbs, hand movements (opening and closing), pronation–supination, and finger tapping [6]. However, these assessments are often highly dependent on clinical expertise and are limited by inter-rater variability, particularly among less experienced clinicians [6]. Thus, integrating objective and reproducible assessment tools can significantly enhance clinical decision-making.

Considering the high cost, technical complexity, and infrastructure requirements of many traditional diagnostic methods, a simple pen-and-paper test combined with computational analysis represents a promising, low-cost, scalable solution for diagnosis, continuous monitoring, and rehabilitation in PD.

II. Materials and Methods

A. Data acquisition

The experimental protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee under process number 69064623.0.0000.5152. The current sample includes 14 individuals in the control group (8 women and 6 men) and 15 individuals in the PD group (8 women and 7 men), aged between 55 and 85 years. In the control group, the mean age was 62.9 years (standard deviation: 10.7), while in the PD group, the mean age was 63.4 years (standard deviation: 9.9). A statistical comparison of age between the groups revealed no significant difference ($p = 0.89$, Student's t -test).

With regard to gender distribution, the control group included 7 men and 6 women, and the PD group comprised 8 men and 7 women. The Hoehn & Yahr (H&Y) scale, a clinical measure of Parkinson's disease progression, yielded a mean score of 1.6 (standard deviation: 0.5) for the PD group, indicating participants were in the early to moderate stages of the disease. The control group presented an H&Y score of zero.

Multiple data collection sessions (at least 16) were conducted throughout the study. In each session, participants

were instructed to draw five consecutive spirals using a pen and paper. In total, 2,567 drawings were collected—1,665 from the PD group and 902 from the control group. Researchers randomly replicated and transformed certain drawings using rotation-based data augmentation techniques to augment the dataset and improve the robustness of the machine learning models.

This procedure was repeated monthly over the course of 16 months to monitor potential changes in the participants' drawing patterns. All documents were subsequently scanned for digital analysis. During the first data collection session, the MDS-UPDRS Part III and the Hoehn & Yahr (H&Y) scales were administered immediately following the drawing task.

The longitudinal testing period extended over 16 months, with participants completing the drawing task once per month to track variations in motor performance over time. After each session, all sheets were scanned and archived.

Post-digitisation, the CorelDRAW software was employed to isolate and standardise each individual spiral into separate image files. Minor retouching was performed to correct distortions while preserving the integrity of the original drawings for subsequent analysis using machine learning models.

B. Data processing and the classification of the groups

For the initial analysis, we selected the MATLAB platform to perform data processing using the Transfer Learning App, which was configured based on a pretrained model widely cited in the literature (DESIPIO, 2023 [7])—VGG16. Introduced by Simonyan and Zisserman during the ILSVRC–2014 competition, the VGG-16 architecture achieved an accuracy of 92.7

Although the depth of the VGG-16 network was increased compared to its predecessors, it maintains architectural similarities to earlier successful models such as AlexNet and LeNet. With larger datasets and tasks involving image recognition, this architecture demonstrated improved performance. This implementation enabled the extraction of more meaningful features from the spiral drawing dataset developed in this study [5].

The first stage of this study involved feature extraction using MATLAB and Python. The selected CNN architectures included VGG16, ResNet50, Xception, MobileNetV1, and an additional instance of ResNet50. The feature extraction layers used were based on established configurations available in the literature:

- VGG16: `fc7`
- ResNet50: `avg_pool`
- Xception: `block14_sepconv2_act`
- Second ResNet50: `global_average_pooling2d_1`
- MobileNetV1: `avg`

The training and testing datasets were defined according to the default configuration settings provided by the MATLAB tool, resulting in a 70% training / 30% testing split. From this setup, we obtained training accuracy and loss metrics, which confirmed that the neural networks demonstrated high reliability and learning capability.

Using the same feature extraction methods, two separate classification tasks were carried out:

1. Differentiation between individuals with Parkinson’s disease and those in the control group.
2. Staging the severity of Parkinson’s disease within the PD group, based on classifications derived from the Hoehn & Yahr scale, as assessed by a certified physiotherapist at the time of data collection.

The accuracy and F1-scores were extracted to evaluate the performance of each CNN architecture across both classification tasks. For enhanced analysis, F1-scores were used as the principal metric to compare the classification capabilities of the different machine learning models.

III. RESULTS

The results, including training accuracy, testing accuracy, recall, and F1-scores for each CNN model, are presented in Figures 1, 2, and 3. Figure 4 illustrates the classification performance metrics (F1-Score, Precision, and Recall) across 16 data collection sessions for both the Control Group (CG) and the Parkinson’s Disease (PD) group.

It is important to highlight that a custom dataset was specifically generated for this study. Initially, we present the consolidated performance metrics, followed by a detailed analysis of model behavior across all data collection sessions, facilitating longitudinal performance comparisons.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Generalization and Overfitting in CNN Models

The evaluation of training and testing metrics provides key insights into the generalization capabilities of the tested CNN models. Improves conciseness performance on training data, their performance on testing data declined significantly, suggesting overfitting.

For example:

- ResNet50’s F1-score dropped from 0.9969 (training) to 0.2873 (testing)
- VGG16’s F1-score dropped from 0.9972 (training) to 0.2514 (testing)

These results underscore a significant overfitting issue, demonstrating that elevated training accuracy does not inherently result in effective generalisation for novel data. This disparity indicates that the models might be detecting dataset-specific noise instead of genuinely representative characteristics. To alleviate overfitting, one can implement tactics such as dropout (to diminish neurone co-adaptation), weight decay (to punish excessively complex models), and early stopping (to terminate training prior to the escalation of overfitting). Furthermore, employing a more varied approach to data augmentation—incorporating techniques like rotation, scaling, and noise injection—may improve the model’s resilience by mimicking a broader spectrum of real-world variances [8].

The Xception model—and to a lesser extent ResNet50—exhibited smaller discrepancies between training and testing results, suggesting somewhat better generalization. Nevertheless, overfitting remains a key limitation across all models evaluated.

B. Metric-Based Model Evaluation

An analysis based on F1-scores revealed Xception as the most balanced model overall. While ResNet50 achieved the highest test precision (0.2892) and recall (0.3069), its F1-score (0.2873) was only marginally higher than that of Xception (0.2483), emphasizing its susceptibility to false positives.

Although ResNet50 demonstrated strong recall, indicating high sensitivity in detecting PD cases, it did so at the expense of lower precision. In contrast, MobileNetV2 yielded the lowest F1-score (0.2435), indicating the limitations of lightweight architectures in capturing complex motor pattern features inherent to PD.

C. Performance Across Data Collections

As shown in Figure 4, performance metrics were analyzed across all 16 data collection sessions. The Xception model consistently outperformed all others in terms of F1-score, precision, and recall, particularly within the PD group, highlighting its robustness against temporal variability.

Conversely, VGG16 and ResNet50 exhibited greater variability across sessions, especially when analyzing data from PD participants. While ResNet50 maintained moderately stable performance, its overall effectiveness remained limited.

These patterns suggest that Xception adapts more effectively to temporal shifts in motor behavior, while other architectures are more sensitive to data heterogeneity and session-based fluctuations.

D. Group-Level Classification: CG vs. PD

In the comparison between the Control Group (CG) and the Parkinson’s Disease (PD) group, Xception showed enhanced performance, especially in the precise identification of PD cases. Its ability to identify nuanced clinical patterns establishes it as the most proficient model for differentiating disease stages. Despite ResNet50 demonstrating high recall, its F1-score was inconsistent. The inconsistency mostly resulted from a high false-positive rate, undermining precision. VGG16 and ResNet50 achieved only moderate to subpar performance. These results make them less appropriate for this categorisation assignment.

A crucial factor in executing binary classification between PD and CG groups is the lack of intermediate or organised clinical data to inform the learning process. Stage-based comparisons, such as those using Hoehn and Yahr (H&Y) scores, facilitate progressive stratification and help models recognise incremental pathogenic trends. The binary classification framework presents restricted internal variability.

In the absence of distinct transitional characteristics or ongoing clinical indicators of disease progression, the model is limited to deriving insights solely from fundamental image-level variations. Such distinctions may fail to encompass the complete complexity of Parkinson’s disease. As a result, machine learning algorithms developed

Fig. 1. Comparison of Training vs. Testing F1-Score by Model. The results show a large gap between training (red) and testing (dark green) performance for all models, indicating overfitting.

Fig. 2. Comparison of Training vs. Testing Precision by Model. Precision on the test set is consistently low across all models, with ResNet50 achieving the highest value.

Fig. 3. Comparison of Training vs. Testing Recall by Model. Similar to precision, recall on the test set is low, with ResNet50 exhibiting the highest recall among the evaluated models.

Fig. 4. Metrics (Precision, Recall, and F1-Score) across 16 Data Collections, comparing the Parkinson's Disease group (PD, in orange) and the Control group (CG, in gray) for each model.

within these limitations are susceptible to underfitting or overfitting, leading to inferior classification performance, in this case, we can see the overfitting in the classification performance was the problem that occurred. This discovery underscores the essential requirement for supplementary variables or biomarkers to facilitate model training and improve generalisation.

E. Final Considerations

Model selection must consider both the application context and performance trade-offs. Xception emerges as the most promising candidate for clinical deployment, offering a balanced combination of precision, recall, and generalization. ResNet50, due to its computational efficiency, may be suitable for real-time or embedded systems, provided that moderate diagnostic accuracy is acceptable. However, VGG16, despite its stability, does not demonstrate competitive performance in this context.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presented a comparative evaluation of four convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures—VGG16, Xception, ResNet50, and MobileNetV2—for classifying hand-drawn spiral images from individuals with Parkinson’s Disease and healthy controls. Xception consistently outperformed the other models, exhibiting high generalization capabilities, robust performance across data collections, and strong discrimination of disease-specific patterns. ResNet50 demonstrated potential for detecting PD cases due to its high recall, but its effectiveness was limited by overfitting and lower precision. While ResNet50’s lightweight architecture holds promise for portable applications, it does so at the cost of reduced classification accuracy. VGG16, although stable, did not yield competitive results overall.

These findings underscore the importance of balancing diagnostic accuracy, generalization ability, and computational efficiency when deploying AI-based tools in real-world clinical settings. Future work should investigate techniques such as transfer learning, regularization methods, ensemble modeling, and multimodal data fusion to further enhance classification performance and model robustness.

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